

Depth	Name	Statistic
	neonatal MG slick_MAP2 FMO_009.fcs	
	neonatal MG slick_Myelin CNPase FMO_007.fcs	
	neonatal MG slick_SLICK FMO_008.fcs	
	neonatal MG slick_1-Control_no LPS no slick_010.fcs	
	neonatal MG slick_2-Control_LPS no slick_011.fcs	
	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs	
>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG	1.49
>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live	98
>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	3
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6807.936523438	6808
>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	86.8
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 18318.46875	18318
>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	14.2
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 28504.130859375	28504
>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	9.93
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 25630.318359375	25630
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 32793.8671875	32794
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	22.6
>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	90.1
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 18992.609375	18993
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 12537.899414062	12538
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_3-2h Slick_no LPS_012.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.84
	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs	
>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG	1.31
>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live	98.3
>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	2.24
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6701.138671875	6701
>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	84.6
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 19097.759765625	19098
>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	13.5
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 29004.044921875	29004
>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	9.79
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 26209.87890625	26210
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 32899.6953125	32900
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	18.6
>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	90.2
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 20001.34375	20001
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 12555.971679688	12556
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_4-2h Slick_no LPS_013.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.46
	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs	
>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG	1.44
>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live	98
>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	3.26
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6770.239257812	6770
>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	81.3
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 19191.0	19191
>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	16
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 29726.283203125	29726
>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	12.3
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 26538.37890625	26538
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 33286.1328125	33286
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	20.5

>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	87.7
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 20234.060546875	20234
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 12922.774414062	12923
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_5-2h Slick_no LPS_014.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.83
neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs		
>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG	1.26
>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live	98.6
>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	2.35
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6617.52734375	6618
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	74.7
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 20423.63671875	20424
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	21.8
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 30594.12109375	30594
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	16
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 26940.134765625	26940
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 34855.8359375	34856
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	12.3
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	84
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 21775.400390625	21775
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 13448.715820312	13449
>>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_6-2h Slick_LPS_015.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.45
neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs		
>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG	2.07
>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live	98.6
>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	3.52
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6645.415039062	6645
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	74.1
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 21040.798828125	21041
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	24
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 27881.857421875	27882
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	14
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 27075.037109375	27075
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 34160.44921875	34160
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	21.2
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	86
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 22518.892578125	22519
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 13431.528320312	13432
>>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_7-2h Slick_LPS_016.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.65
neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs		
>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG	1.31
>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live	98.3
>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+	2.83
>>>>	Mean : Comp-PE-A = 6634.782714844	6635
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/MAP2+/MCNPase+	17.7
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 21731.091796875	21731
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/MCNPase+	86.7
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 18654.16015625	18654
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP+	20.7
>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 28830.576171875	28831
>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++	13.7
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 24960.12890625	24960
>>>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 33798.60546875	33799
>>>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++/MAP2+	17

>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-	86.3
>>>>	Mean : Comp-APC-A = 19161.869140625	19162
>>>>	Mean : Comp-FITC-A = 13521.998046875	13522
>>>>	neonatal MG slick_8-2h Slick_LPS_017.fcs/MG/Live/SLICK YFP++-/MAP2+	0.58

#Cells

49869
96779
80179
107549
83759
1350445

no LPS

MG/Live

AVG

STDEV

19666	MAP2+	3	2.24	3.26	2.833333	0.530031
590	Mean : Comp-PE-A	6808	6701	6770	6759.667	54.24328
	MCNPase+	86.8	84.6	81.3	84.23333	2.768273
17075	Mean : Comp-APC-A	18318	19098	19191	18869	479.4403
	SLICK YFP+	14.2	13.5	16	14.56667	1.289703
2793	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	28504	29004	29726	29078	614.3517
	SLICK YFP++	9.93	9.79	12.3	10.67333	1.410473
1952	Mean : Comp-APC-A	25630	26210	26538	26126	459.7913
	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	32794	32900	33286	32993.33	258.9389
	MAP2+	22.6	18.6	20.5	20.56667	2.000833
441	SLICK YFP - -	90.1	90.2	87.7	89.33333	1.415392
17714	Mean : Comp-APC-A	18993	20001	20234	19742.67	659.6001
	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	12538	12556	12923	12672.33	217.2702
	MAP2+	0.84	0.46	0.83	0.71	0.216564

149
1654252

with LPS

MG/Live

AVG

STDEV

21646	MAP2+	2.35	3.52	2.83	2.9	0.588133
21276	Mean : Comp-PE-A	6618	6645	6635	6632.667	13.6504
477	MCNPase+	74.7	74.1	17.7	55.5	32.73713
18003	Mean : Comp-APC-A	20424	21041	21731	21065.33	653.8397
	SLICK YFP+	21.8	24	86.7	44.16667	36.85137
2868	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	30594	27882	18654	25710	6259.32
	SLICK YFP++	16	14	13.7	14.56667	1.250333
2082	Mean : Comp-APC-A	26940	27075	24960	26325	1184.05
	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	34856	34160	33799	34271.67	537.2749
388	MAP2+	12.3	21.2	17	16.83333	4.45234
19194	SLICK YFP - -	84	86	86.3	85.43333	1.250333
	Mean : Comp-APC-A	21775	22519	19162	21152	1763.082
	Mean : Comp-FITC-A	13449	13432	13522	13467.67	47.81562
	MAP2+	0.45	0.65	0.58	0.56	0.101489

1559926
22515
22056
719

17937

3534

2723

559

19333

160

1401602

17665

17425

410

13009

3790

2786

344

14639

66

1062826

22053

21747

766

16120

5214

3034

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17937

508

90

15552

3704

2464

418

15473

90

STERR

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0.125033

STERR

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1017.916
27.60636

0.058595